

REIMAGINING DECARBONIZATION THROUGH COUNTER- MAPPING:

Addressing Conflict in Ecological Transitions

ERZE DINARAMA

Independent Researcher
erzadinarama@gmail.com

KEYWORDS

Counter-Mapping, Tension Mapping, Renaturalization, Socio-Ecological Transition, Conflict Spaces, Ecological Governance

ABSTRACT

As cities across Europe and beyond undertake large-scale renaturalization projects, including reopening rivers and creating ecological corridors, the paradox of ecological transition becomes more evident. These projects, while designed to combat climate change and restore natural ecosystems, entail significant carbon costs, land-use conflicts, and socio-ecological trade-offs during their implementation phases. This paper proposes tension mapping as an essential design methodology for addressing these contradictions, offering a way to visually and systematically reveal the conflict spaces inherent in such projects. By combining critical analysis with proactive design strategies, tension mapping integrates spatial, social, and ecological perspectives. Drawing from a speculative case study of river renaturalization in Lausanne, this work argues for an approach that acknowledges the hidden costs and challenges of ecological transitions while fostering transparency, accountability, and critical engagement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Amid escalating climate change and biodiversity loss, cities across Europe and beyond are embracing renaturalization and ecological restoration projects aimed at restoring natural ecosystems, reintroducing biodiversity, and bolstering climate resilience. However, despite their environmental intentions, these projects often entail significant carbon costs, land-use conflicts, and socio-ecological trade-offs. From the removal of concrete and asphalt to the re-engineering of urban landscapes, the pursuit of “going back” to “nature” paradoxically introduces substantial emissions and spatial transformations that generate conflicts.

Decades of implementing so-called 'green' projects have revealed that these initiatives are neither inherently beneficial nor free of unintended consequences. Concepts like green grabbing, greenwashing, and biodiversity compensation areas highlight the unintended consequences of these interventions. Similarly, traditional environmental evaluations—such as Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) and Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs)—often obscure the spatial and temporal complexities of these projects, treating them as administrative formalities rather than opportunities for critical engagement.

This paper proposes tension mapping as an essential design methodology to address these contradictions, offering a framework to systematically and visually reveal the conflict spaces inherent in ecological projects. By challenging the dominant narrative that such initiatives are intrinsically “green” or “good,” this approach exposes the hidden carbon costs, spatial disruptions, and ecological trade-offs often overlooked in conventional assessments.

Tension mapping introduces a dual-mapping strategy: one map outlines the project's intended ecological design goals, while the second highlights the inherent conflicts, contradictions, and trade-offs. By moving beyond the limitations of traditional environmental evaluations—which are often treated as administrative formalities—tension mapping redefines these assessments as core design methodologies.

This paper draws on a speculative case study of river renaturalization in Lausanne to demonstrate how tension mapping can integrate spatial complexities into ecological transition proposals. By addressing conflicts rather than minimizing them, this approach fosters a nuanced methodology for navigating socio-ecological transformations.

Recognizing the multifaceted nature of these challenges, tension mapping ultimately seeks to reclaim spatial representation in ecological projects, promoting critical transparency and situated responses.

2. RENATURALIZATION: A CRITICAL FOCUS

Renaturalization has become institutionalized not only as a funding mechanism and policy objective but also through legally binding commitments that position it as one of the central pillars of contemporary environmental strategies. This institutionalization makes it a critical topic for analysis and debate, as well as for assessment from diverse perspectives within spatial practices.

In August 2024, the EU's Nature Restoration Law came into effect, marking the first continent-wide, comprehensive legislation of its kind. This law establishes binding targets to restore degraded ecosystems, aiming to cover at least 20% of the EU's land and sea areas by 2030 and all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050. At the global scale, the United Nations Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021–2030) complements these initiatives, promoting efforts to prevent, halt, and reverse ecosystem degradation worldwide.

Although practices resembling nature restoration have historical precedents, renaturalization as a distinct ecological concept emerged in the 1970s. By the late 20th century, it became a key strategy for rehabilitating heavily modified landscapes in Europe, such as river and wetland restoration projects in Germany. Today, renaturalization is central to achieving goals related to biodiversity conservation and climate resilience, reinforced by extensive funding mechanisms like the Recovery and Resilience Facility and Horizon Europe.

Today, renaturalization is central to initiatives such as the EU Nature Restoration Law (European Commission, 2024) and the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021–2030) (UNEP, 2024). These frameworks reflect a growing recognition of the need to restore ecosystems through practices that address ecological, social, and spatial complexities.

Renaturalization has undeniably become an established pillar of contemporary environmental strategies, and its significance is evident in the urgent need to address degraded ecosystems, restore biodiversity, and bolster climate resilience. However, as these projects gain momentum, it becomes increasingly apparent that ecological transition initiatives are far from straightforward. While their goals are commendable, the path to achieving them is fraught with complexities, conflicts, and unintended consequences that demand careful consideration.

This raises an essential question: how do we, as spatial practitioners, navigate these challenges? How can we critically engage with renaturalization to not only mitigate its trade-offs but also reimagine how such initiatives are conceptualized, designed, and implemented?

Methodologies like tension mapping offer an opportunity to rethink the approach to renaturalization, providing a lens to address its inherent tensions and envision more transparent and accountable design practices.

3. TENSION MAPPING AS AN INTEGRAL DESIGN TOOL

Tension mapping builds upon and extends the principles of counter-mapping, offering a proactive design methodology specifically tailored to address the complexities and conflicts inherent in socio-ecological transitions. However, it extends these principles into the realm of ecological design, adapting it as a tool for addressing the inherent conflicts and contradictions in ecological transition projects. By incorporating dual maps—one visualizing intended design goals and another exposing conflict spaces—this approach transforms mapping into a design methodology that not only critiques but informs ecological transition design processes.

Counter-mapping, rooted in critical cartography and political ecology, emerged as a way for marginalized communities to challenge dominant spatial narratives. Like counter-mapping, tension mapping reveals hidden conflicts and spatial contradictions—social, ecological, or carbon-related—embedded in renaturalization efforts. It critiques the neutrality of traditional environmental assessments, highlighting biases, oversimplifications, and omissions that obscure the complexities of ecological transitions.

Urban designers such as Paola Viganò have explored counter-projects to reimagine futures by proposing alternatives to dominant trajectories. Building on this tradition, tension mapping serves as both critique and a platform for envisioning alternative ecological futures. It also draws inspiration from controversy mapping, developed by Bruno Latour, which visualizes disputes and uncertainties before they become stabilized or “black-boxed”. However, where controversy mapping describes conflicts, tension mapping integrates them into the design process itself.

Showing the unintended environmental consequences of projects is not a new concept. Over the decades, frameworks such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), first conceptualized in the 1960s and formalized in the 1990s through the ISO 14040 standards (ISO, 2006), and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), mandated by the 1985 EIA Directive (85/337/EEC) in Europe (EUR-Lex, 1985), have become foundational tools in environmental governance. These methodologies provide structured approaches to evaluating trade-offs and impacts, assessing ecosystem effects, and quantifying environmental footprints across lifecycles.

While essential for evaluating environmental impacts, these frameworks can inadvertently contribute to greenwashing. For instance, the flexibility in LCA to adjust system boundaries based

on specific goals allows selective framing that may obscure or exclude certain environmental dimensions. Similarly, tools like EIA often emphasize regulatory compliance over providing a holistic understanding of environmental impacts. Furthermore, these methodologies rarely incorporate the spatial dimension of environmental projects, leaving critical gaps in understanding their broader implications.

Originally designed for large-scale industrial or infrastructural developments, these frameworks face challenges when applied to renaturalization projects. Unlike conventional projects, renaturalization aims to address environmental challenges yet often operates under the paradox of contributing to new impacts. Moreover, these frameworks, while integral to governance, have been co-opted into offsetting schemes that present actions as environmentally neutral while masking deeper socio-ecological consequences.

Unlike conventional environmental assessments, which often remain limited to administrative checklists and serve more bureaucratic than critical purposes, tension mapping treats these assessments as design endeavors in themselves. Through tension mapping, renaturalization becomes more than a solution-oriented exercise; it evolves into a space of negotiation, where tensions are made visible, actionable, and integral to the design logic. This methodology becomes essential when proposing ecological restoration projects because it actively engages with the conflict spaces—the spaces where environmental benefits clash with carbon emissions, social spaces, valuable agricultural land, or other unintended consequences.

4. CASE STUDY: A SPECULATIVE PROPOSAL FOR THE RESURFACING OF LAUSANNE'S RIVER

In Switzerland, extensive canalization of rivers during the 19th and 20th centuries, driven by urbanization and industrialization, significantly altered the natural hydrology of waterways. These modifications often confined rivers into narrow channels, disconnecting them from their floodplains and natural ecosystems. While these interventions served their immediate purposes, they also led to unintended environmental consequences. Exactly because of this historical legacy of extensive canalization, Switzerland has made 'renaturalization' one of the objectives of its water management strategy. Today, it is actively addressing these historical impacts through approximately 100 renaturalization projects aimed at restoring rivers. Accompanying these ecological and practical motivations is a shift in public sentiment.

Lausanne's Flon and Louve rivers, gradually canalized over two centuries, illustrate this transformation. Initially driven by sanitation, flood control, and urban expansion, river coverage extended beyond immediate necessity, eventually replacing watercourses with roads,

highways, and low-density neighborhoods. These changes not only altered the city's landscape but also its relationship with natural systems.

Figure 1:
Construction of a tunnel for the Flon River underway in Lausanne. Source: Quartier-du-Flon Archives.

The canalization of rivers has disrupted natural hydrological cycles, intensified flooding and overflow events, and contributed to the formation of urban heat islands. It has also placed significant strain on wastewater infrastructure, often exceeding its capacity during heavy precipitation and leading to lake pollution. Moreover, canalization has resulted in the loss of habitats for species reliant on water systems. All of this is further exacerbated by climate change, which amplifies extreme weather events, heightens urban heat stress, and accelerates biodiversity loss. These challenges underscore the necessity of strategies like the renaturalization of waterways. Managing water infrastructure is thus envisioned not merely as a technical solution or compliance with national directives but as a critical necessity.

Given these complexities, exploring alternative approaches to mitigate the impacts of canalization becomes essential. For this reason, a speculative scenario focusing on the renaturalization of rivers has been developed. While fully bringing water back to the surface is no longer feasible, this exercise considers partial resurfacing as a design scenario, examining its implications through the lens of water management and addressing the associated trade-offs.

The project proposes a speculative and layered approach to the resurfacing and renaturalization of the Flon and Louve rivers, building on their historical pathways where Lausanne's topography still supports water flow.

Figure 2: The pathways of the rivers before any canalization, showcasing their courses as they existed prior to any canalization. The watershed is utilized as a system boundary, serving as a framework to provide proper voice and space to the river.

Figure 3: Over the course of 300 years, the river was progressively covered and engineered. This transformation saw the river's role transition from defense to industry to waste disposal and, finally, to becoming a canalized component of the city's water management system.

However, in the southern part, where urban density and the complexity of the urban fabric make it impossible to follow the original route, new pathways are envisioned to bypass these constraints. To ensure a continuous connection and the creation of a delta, the project introduces the provocative concept of piping infrastructure in areas where the City of Lausanne is currently planning an underground pedestrian network. This hybrid system of visible and subterranean waterways sparks a dialogue about spatial compromises, aiming to reconnect the rivers with Lake Geneva while addressing spatial limitations.

By creating a hybrid system of waterways, this approach aims to restore natural water flows, reconnect the rivers with Lake Geneva, and foster continuous links across the watershed—bridging upstream

Figure 4: The Louve River is diverted into a pipe and sent to Lake Geneva, while the Flon River is redirected through a pipe and eventually discharged into the Vuachère River. Where the rivers once flowed, their former paths are now occupied by underground sewage systems.

areas, urban environments, and the lakeshore—while strengthening biodiversity and enhancing urban resilience.

Bringing water to the surface would also help improve soil health, mitigate flooding, support biodiversity, increase carbon sequestration, restore natural infiltration, regulate temperature, recharge groundwater, and filter pollutants. However, even partial renaturalization of rivers in Lausanne presents significant tensions and challenges. The current urban fabric is densely interwoven with infrastructure, public spaces, and existing uses that conflict with the goals of renaturalization. Over time, most river paths have been covered by roads, driven by the convenience of expanding urban mobility networks. Major roads and mobility corridors now occupy former riverbeds, and any attempt to restore natural waterways must contend with disruptions to transportation systems and connectivity.

Figure 5: The proposal envisions a “new” river that runs parallel to the existing underground water infrastructure, complementing and working in tandem with it. This new river pathway aligns with areas where water still flows on the surface, leveraging the topography as a guiding element.

Agricultural areas now rely on the space provided by canalized rivers, which allowed for expanded production efficiency. Renaturalization efforts in these zones would lead to the loss of arable land, disruption of farming practices, and the risk of waterlogging or altered soil composition, potentially displacing farming activities. These shifts are further complicated by carbon emissions from machinery use and soil disturbances. Urban streets and infrastructure require unsealing and realignment, creating additional emissions from demolition, reconstruction, and associated soil disturbances. Constructing new pipe infrastructure to connect and manage water flows introduces additional complexity, including maintenance challenges and extreme carbon costs from manufacturing, installation, and construction activities. While necessary for ensuring continuous flow downstream, reliance on piping systems perpetuates long-term dependencies and their associated challenges.

Figure 6: This mapping represents the immediate conflicts between the resurfacing and renaturalization of rivers and their existing surroundings, categorized by the type of impacted zone—ranging from agricultural areas to periurban zones, densely built environments, and the lakeshore. On the left, the mapping highlights the carbon costs of these interventions, emphasizing the environmental trade-offs involved. Together, these layers expose the multidimensional sacrifices and challenges inherent in such projects, making the complexities and compromises of ecological transitions visible.

Urban parks, heritage sites, and recreational facilities have taken root in areas previously defined by waterways. These spaces, integral to Lausanne's identity, present another layer of tension, as renaturalization risks disrupting valuable public spaces, recreational facilities, and community activities. Balancing ecological restoration with the preservation of these spaces raises critical questions about priorities and trade-offs. Furthermore, renaturalization would require extensive engineering interventions, such as removing impermeable surfaces, modifying topography, and constructing new water paths. These actions result in significant carbon emissions, soil disruptions, and changes to local ecosystems.

The dense urbanization in central Lausanne adds further complications, requiring interventions to navigate a crowded landscape of buildings, utilities, and infrastructure systems. Each of these interventions, whether in agricultural land or dense urban zones, presents significant tensions and entails notable carbon costs.

The case study in Lausanne positions tension mapping as a lens for exploring design methodologies, particularly in the context of ecological transitions and renaturation. The preliminary mapping serves as both a demonstrative exercise and an invitation to adopt a dual framework methodology. In an era where greenwashing often oversimplifies ecological interventions, this approach provides a lens to not only evaluate, but transparently reveal both the benefits and trade-offs.

5. CONCLUSIONS

As the climate crisis intensifies, cities and designers are increasingly called upon to create projects that restore ecosystems. However, as this paper argues, these projects are not without their contradictions and hidden costs. By integrating tension mapping as a core design methodology, ecological projects can move beyond the narrow focus of regulatory compliance and adopt a more nuanced, accountable, and critically transparent approach to ecological transition initiatives.

This methodology allows for a comprehensive understanding of projects by making visible the often-hidden carbon costs, social disruptions, and ecological trade-offs. By fostering transparency, tension mapping ensures greater accountability among stakeholders, offering a responsible alternative to the superficial narratives of sustainability that often dominate. Moreover, it actively engages with the complexity of socio-ecological transitions rather than oversimplifying them, facilitating a more nuanced approach to their benefits and challenges.

Rather than promoting projects as purely beneficial or sustainable, tension mapping provides a platform for addressing the inherent tensions and conflicts of these transitions.

It encourages designers to not only acknowledge the costs of “going back” to “nature” but also to integrate these insights into broader discourses on ecological governance, sustainability, and degrowth.

REFERENCES

- Council of Europe. (2000). European Landscape Convention. Retrieved from <https://www.coe.int/en/web/landscape>
- Davis, B., Maraña, M., Giardino, L., Schmid, W., & Stoppel, F. (Eds.). (2022). *Zones of Tension: The Cultivation of Transdisciplinary Practices*. Humboldt Books.
- EPFL Habitat Research Center. (n.d.). *New Climates in Lausanne: Hidden Rivers*. Retrieved from https://www.epfl.ch/research/domains/habitat/new-climates-in-lausanne/?utm_source=chatgpt.com.
- ETH Zurich MAS UTD. (n.d.). *Resurfacing Water and Its Stories: The Emergence of a Socio-ecological Threshold for an Urban Watershed*. Retrieved from <https://mas-utd.arch.ethz.ch/Programme/Student-Work/Recreating-The-Watershed>.
- EUR-Lex. (1985). Directive 85/337/EEC – Environmental Impact Assessment. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A31985L0337>.
- European Commission. (2024). *Horizon Europe: The EU Research and Innovation Programme*. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020>
- European Commission. (2024). *Nature Restoration Law enters into force*. Published August 15, 2024. Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/news/nature-restoration-law-enters-force-2024-08-15_en
- Federal Council of Switzerland. (1992). *Federal Act on the Protection of Waters*. Retrieved from https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/1992/1860_1860_1860/en.
- Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN). (n.d.). *Renaturation of Waterways*. Retrieved from <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/water/info-specialists/measures-for-water-protection/renaturierung-der-gewaesser.html>.
- ISO. (2006). *ISO 14040: Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – Principles and framework*. Retrieved from <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html>.
- Jordan, W. R., III, & Lubick, G. M. (2011). *Making Nature Whole: A History of Ecological Restoration*. Island Press.

- Latour, B. (2009). Mapping Controversies on Science for Politics. Retrieved from <https://web.archive.org/web/20150314225840/http://mappingcontroversies.net/Home/AboutMacospol>.
- Peluso, N. L. (1995). Whose Woods Are These? Counter-Mapping Forest Territories in Kalimantan, Indonesia. *Antipode*, 27(4), 383–406.
- Quartier du Flon. (n.d.). Histoire du Flon. Retrieved from <https://flon.ch/fr/a-propos-du-flon/quartier/histoire/>
- Research and Innovation. (2024). European Structural and Investment Funds. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/funding/erdf/
- UN General Assembly. (2024). United Nations Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021–2030), Resolution 73/284. Retrieved from <https://undocs.org/en/A/RES/73/284>
- United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). (2024). UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration 2021–2030. Retrieved from <https://www.decadeonrestoration.org>
- UNEP. (2002). Environmental Impact Assessment and Strategic Environmental Assessment Guidelines. Retrieved from https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/8753/Environmental_impact_assessment.pdf.
- Viganò, P. (2024). Transition in Chablais. Retrieved from <https://mas-utd.arch.ethz.ch/Programme/Studios/Hs-24-Transition-In-Chablais>.
- Wessolek, G. (2002). The Development of River Renaturation Projects in Germany. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 45(4), 551–567.
- Yaneva, A. (2021). The New Studio: A Mapping Controversies Experiment. In J. Silberberger (Ed.), *Against and for Method: Revisiting Architectural Design as Research* (pp. 171–186). GTA Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.54872/gta/4550-09>.